

BURDEN OF DISEASE ASSESSMENT FOR NON-FERROUS METAL INDUSTRY AIR EMISSIONS AT A LOCAL SCALE

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Air quality policy should aim to lower emissions of air pollutants in the most effective, cost-efficient, and evidence-based approach possible, focusing on controlling relevant emissions and sources and on identifying the most adequate and proportionate actions to improve air quality. This can be achieved by quantifying source/sector specific health impacts and then assessing the feasibility and relevance of measures aiming at reducing or controlling emissions.

The objective of this study is to quantify the sector-specific impact of the air emissions associated with the activities of the European NFM (non-ferrous metals) industry on human exposure and health. This is done by collecting data on factory emissions, estimating their ground-level concentrations, modelling the population attributable exposure fraction and the relative health impact in terms of Disability Adjusted Life Years (DALYs) by following the Burden of Disease (BoD) approach as recommended by the World Health Organisation (WHO) (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Study workflow consisting of four main parts and comparison of the health impact with air pollution health burden in Europe.

Methods

Cause-related air pollution health impact assessment requires information on emissions, dispersion of pollutants, exposed population, and exposure-response functions to assess health loss in DALYs. Here, the assessment was performed for NFM industrial emissions for years 2019 and 2020. The assessment reveals the European NFM industry emissions contribution to the air pollution health burden. The methods consist of the following parts:

- **Emissions:**
 - o The assessment is based on the emissions data reported in the European Pollutant Release and Transfer Register (E-PRTR).
 - o An aggregated emission evaluation was performed because not all relevant parameters were available for pollution transfer calculations.
 - o The NFM-emissions were described with a single chimney that was parametrized by using emission weighted stack properties.
 - o Fugitive emissions were not included in the analysis due to data gaps.
- **Air concentrations and exposure:**
 - o Dispersion modeling was performed at local scale (area of 40 km by 40 km) by using a Gaussian plume model.
 - o The population in the model region (1,600 km²) was set at 800,000, corresponding to population density of 500 persons/km². This was chosen to have a realistic, representative worse-case scenario for European countries.
- **Human health impacts:**

- All pollutants were considered for which exposure-response functions were available. For NFM industry emissions, 17 of the total 24 pollutants had exposure response functions.
- Health endpoints considered are particulate matter (PM) natural-cause mortality and lower respiratory symptoms for school children, SO₂ lung cancer, NO_x natural-cause mortality, CO ischemic heart disease, cancer for Ni, Cr (as Cr^{VI}), Cd, As, and Pb, cancer for C₆H₆, BaP, dioxins, naphthalene, polychlorinated biphenyls (PCBs), tetrachloroethylene, trichloroethylene and dichloromethane.
- CO₂ and methane emissions were exempted from the human health evaluation.
- Environmental damage was not evaluated.

- DALY calculations:

- Human health impact via inhalation exposure was quantified by using the widely accepted BoD concept, e.g., by WHO and the European Environmental Agency (EEA).
- The overall burden of disease assessment is performed by calculating DALYs. One DALY represents the loss of the equivalent of one year of full health and it can be used to describe the health gap between the current and an ideal state of health of the population. DALYs allows comparing the burden of disease of the emissions to air associated to the activities of the NFM sector with those of other sectors/activities.
- Central European baseline burden of disease rates for 2019 were applied in DALY calculations (Murray et al., 2020).
- The BoD assessment was performed by following worse-case scenarios and a precautionary approach: DALY discounting or age-weighting was not performed, emissions were assumed to come on top of potential cut-off concentrations, and potential DALY double counting due to NO_x and PM health effects overlap was not taken into account.

Results

For the years 2019 and 2020 were reported 371 and 283 emission measurements based on 106 and 69 facilities, respectively. Total cumulative emissions accounted to 0.51 Mt (megatons) and 0.55 Mt for the years 2019 and 2020, respectively. When excluding CO₂ and methane, the emissions consisted of 88.4% CO, 5.7% NO_x, 3.9% SO_x, 1.2% non-methane volatile organic compounds (NMVOC) and 0.9% of other pollutants for year 2019 and 89.5% CO, 6.8% NO_x, 2.1% SO_x, 1.1% NMVOC and 0.5% of other pollutants for year 2020.

The calculated average annual ground level concentration of NFM emissions was 72.2 µg/m³ at the model area of 1,600 km². Except for CO, the ground level concentrations were below the EEA's ambient air quality standards. The average concentration was 25 µg/m³ at the edge of the model area. This shows that the population exposure assessment was not complete and the model area should be extended to capture DALYs outside the current model region.

The estimated NFM-industry air emissions health impact was 1,430 and 1,446 DALYs for years 2019 and 2020, respectively in the modelled area of 1,600 km². Major cause for DALYs were on average NO_x, (991 DALYs), PM_{2.5} (259 DALYs), and PM_{2.5-10} (133 DALYs) covering 96% of the overall DALY burden at local scale (Table 1). Other relevant pollutants for the health impact were SO_x (28 DALY), CO (25 DALYs), and naphthalene (2.9 DALYs) while others were on average below 1 DALY. Metals, namely Ni, Cr(VI), Cd, As and Pb contribution to DALYs was below 0.015% in total. Natural-cause mortality was caused 66.3% by YLLs and 33.7% by YLDs. From the investigated health endpoints for natural cause mortality, main causes for PM_{2.5} DALYs were ischemic heart disease (IHD) and stroke while for PM_{2.5-10} were IHD, chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD) and stroke. DALY rates for the model population were 179 and 181 DALYs per 100,000 persons (DALYs/10⁵) for the years 2019 and 2020, respectively.

Table 1. Breakdown of the DALYs according to pollutants by total NFM industry in EU at a local scale.

Pollutant group	2019, [DALY]	2020, [DALY]
PM _{2.5} +PM _{2.5-10} (Natural-cause mortality + lower respiratory symptoms for school children)	500	290
Sum of metals: Ni, Cr(VI), Cd, As and Pb	0.21	0.14
Other: SO _x , NO _x , CO, C ₆ H ₆ , BaP, dioxin, naphthalene, PCBs, tetrachloroethylene, and trichloroethylene	928	1159
Total DALYs	1430	1446

Discussion

Benefits of the zero-emission policy is not straightforward to assess as it would require global exposure modelling. However, it can be concluded that at a local scale, the NFM-industry emissions potential to reduce the health impact is ca. 1,440 DALYs per year. The most efficient way for the NFM-industry to reduce DALYs by direct inhalation exposure would be to reduce NO_x and PM emissions, as they cover 96% of the DALYs.

Number of DALY and DALY rate comparison is not straightforward because the exposure model population may vary (e.g., assessment performed only at the hotspot or at whole-country level), health endpoints vary (all cause natural mortality, YLLs, YLDs), pollution components are not the same and underlying assumptions may vary (e.g. cut-off values, DALY discounting, double counting). At local scale, the NFM-industry disease burden including YLD and YLL is ca. 0.04% of YLLs by PM_{2.5} pollution in EU-27 in 2019 (4,097,900 YLLs, as estimated by EEA). NFM industry emissions impact compared to other emission scenarios are generally low both as sum of DALYs or normalized with study population (Figure 1). This means that if the traffic emissions from a large city, e.g., Warsaw with 25,000 DALYs or Barcelona 9,900 DALYs, were to be removed, this would be much more impactful in reducing the life loss, than the removing the whole NFM-industry emissions at local scale (1,440 DALYs). Similar results were found for residential wood combustion, fossil fuel combustion in general, pig farming, and electricity production (Figure 1). This observation is also supported by the key emission category analysis by the EEA.

The NFM-emissions total risk level was 10.2 premature deaths/10⁵ in the local scale and on average 0.12 premature deaths per factory/10⁵. The commonly accepted risk level threshold is 1/10⁵ persons which is not exceeded at an individual factory level. The economic loss associated to the NFM-industry air emissions impact at local scale would be 100.8 million € (excluding CO₂, methane and environmental implications), which can be considered low compared to Industry emissions in general (277 to 433 billion €; including greenhouse gases), road traffic (166 billion €) or domestic heating and cooking activities by households (29 billion €).

Figure 1. Disease burdens estimated for emission scenarios in Europe as A) DALY rate per 10⁵ habitants and B) DALYs. Note, fossil fuel combustion exposure-response function (ERF) for PM_{2.5} is significantly higher than the ERF used by EEA or other studies. Res. Wood comb. is abbreviated from residential wood combustion.

Conclusions and recommendations

Overall, the assessment shows that the impact of NFM-industry emissions is limited compared to other sectors, such as traffic, fossil fuel combustion, residential wood combustion, and pig farming. The NFM-industry's potential to improve air quality is mostly related to the reduction of NO_x and PM emissions.

This evaluation would greatly benefit from individual factories impact assessments at global scale and from including emissions from factories not covered by the obligation of reporting their emissions data in the E-PRTR. Production data and data on economic output would allow assessing the emissions of NFM facilities against their production and cost-benefit for society.

This evaluation allows the estimations of the benefits of target emission objectives compared to the current situation. It is recommended to perform a similar impact assessment for the key emission categories as specified by the EEA to achieve a more objective and effective air quality policy.

Keywords: Non-ferrous metal (NFM) industry, air emissions, burden of disease, health impact, local scale modeling

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1. INTRODUCTION

Air pollution is a major cause of premature death and disease, and it is the single largest environmental health risk in Europe (EEA, 2022a). This represented 4% to 7% of all deaths in 2018 (OECD and European Union, 2020). It is clearly shown that better air quality benefits for society largely outweigh its costs (Trinomics, 2022). This, together with the publication of the new WHO global air quality guidelines in 2021, drove the European Commission (EC) to revise the Ambient Air Quality (AAQ) standards. In November 2019, the Commission published its Fitness Check of the AAQ Directives (2004/107/EC and 2008/50/EC), where it was concluded that the Directives have been only partially effective. The Fitness Check was followed by the European Green Deal (December 2019) and the Zero Pollution Action Plan (ZPAP; September 2021) to improve the air quality in Europe. The ZPAP target is to reduce by 2030 the number of premature deaths due to exposure to fine particulate matter by 55% and to reduce the number of EU ecosystems where air pollution threatens biodiversity by 25% (EC, 2022a). On 26th October 2022, the EC published a set of new proposals, where the revision of the AAQ Directives would merge the Directives into one, and seek to (EC, 2022b):

- Align EU air quality standards more closely with WHO recommendations;
- Further improve the legislative framework (e.g., in relation to penalties, public information, access to justice, etc.);
- Better support local authorities in achieving cleaner air through strengthening air quality monitoring, modelling and plans.

For the revision of the EU AAQ Directives, an economic analysis of environmental policies and analytical support was performed in the context of Better Regulation (Trinomics, 2022). The study applies the BoD concept which is commonly used to estimate risk factors impact on population health loss in a systematic manner e.g., by the World Health Organisation (WHO) (WHO, 2017, 2016) and the current European Union-Health Information System (EU-HIS) (EBoDN, 2022; Haneef et al., 2021). The overall BoD assessment is performed by calculating DALYs, which describes the health gap between the current and an ideal health situation of the population (Box 1). DALY is an absolute metric that enables comparisons of the health impacts of different causes. This allows the estimations of the benefits of target emission objectives compared to the currently prevailing situation (Murray et al., 2020).

BoD calculations are usually based on the **prevailing** concentration levels and the health benefits for **target concentration** levels (Trinomics, 2022). This helps to identify the benefits of pollutant- specific target limit values, e.g., for PM_{2.5}, PM₁₀, NO_x, SO_x, O₃, and which emissions need to be reduced. The current proposal (EC, 2022b) focuses also on emission sources and how they contribute to the exceedance in the national air pollution control programs. However, the proposal (EC, 2022b) does not provide explicit information on emission sector-specific health impacts which also depend on the location of the emission, i.e., population exposure fraction. For example, transportation related emissions occur in densely populated areas while industrial emissions in general come from stacks, at less densely populated areas.

The sector or facility-specific health impact assessment can be used to identify which specific sources or emission sectors have a significant impact on human health, and further, to identify cost-efficient approaches to reduce the health burden associated with air pollution. Such assessment has been made for e.g., fossil fuel combustion (Vohra et al., 2021), transport (Anenberg et al., 2019; Tainio, 2015) and ship emissions (Barregard et al., 2019; Mwase et al., 2020; Viana et al., 2020).

The aim of this study is to have an objective picture of the associated NFM-industry air emissions health impacts at a local scale. This includes the identification of the exposure potential and the health impact assessment based on the BoD concept, the identification of key pollutants causing health loss and quantifying the overall health burden by air pollution and understanding the NFM-industry's potential to improve air quality to design efficient mitigation strategies.

Box 1. The concept of Disability-Adjusted Life Year (DALY)

A DALY is the sum of years of potential life lost due to premature death and the years of productive life lost due to disability compared to a standardised life expectancy. The DALY is a time-based measure that combines years of life lost due to premature mortality (YLLs), years of life lost due to time lived in states of less than full health and years of healthy life lost due to disability (YLDs). One DALY is equivalent to the loss of one healthy life year and the burden of disease is the sum of these DALYs across the population. A DALY can be thought of as the measure of the gap between the current health status and an ideal health situation where the entire population lives to an advanced age, free of disease and disability.

As a matter of illustration of this approach, let us consider a woman with a life expectancy of 84 years in an ideal situation where the population lives to the standard life expectancy and is in perfect health. If the woman faces an alcohol disorder starting at her 40 years leading to premature death in her 50's, the life loss can be calculated in terms of DALYs, and it is equal to the sum of the Years of Life Lost (YLL) due to premature mortality plus the Years Lost due to Disability (YLD). The first component, YLL, is calculated by multiplying the number of deaths in the population due to condition (N) and the standard life expectancy at age of death (L). In this example, $YLL = N \times L = 1 \times (84 - 50) = 34$ (34 years of life lost due to premature death).

The second component, YLD, is calculated by multiplying the number of incident cases (I), in a particular time period, by the average duration of the disease (L) combined with a disability weight factor (DW) which represents the severity of the disease on a scale from 0 (perfect health) to 1 (dead). DW means that, on average, society judges a year with mild back pain (weight 0.02) to be preferable to a year with severe alcohol use disorder (weight 0.57). In this example, $YLD = I \times L \times DW = 1 \times 0,57 \times (50-40) = 5,7$ (5,7 years lived with disabilities). The total loss of healthy years, or DALYs, for the woman with an alcohol disorder is therefore 39,7 years = 34 (YLL) + 5,7 (YLD).

This approach is used to calculate the BoD resulting from air emissions associated with the activities of the NFM sector in terms of DALY, which allow an immediate comparison across other activities and sectors, in order to inform policy-making on the best options to reduce air pollution in the most efficient and effective ways.

2. METHODS

This work is based on available emissions data related to the NFM-industry, and their impact on ground level concentrations at local scale was simulated by using a Gaussian plume model. The assessment is based on an aggregated analysis where all emissions were assumed to be exhausted from a single stack. Aggregated analysis was used to simplify the calculations and to obtain generic results. This applies for all concentrations having linear exposure-response functions. The virtual stack was described using average stack properties and parameters measured in the NFM-industry. Population exposure was described as a constant population density around the facility. Health burden was calculated by using the BoD concept. The local scale health burden was compared with results from other relevant BoD studies and the overall health burden by air pollution in the EU-27.

2.1. INDUSTRIAL EMISSION DATA COLLECTION FROM E-PRTR

For the data collection, an evaluation of the available industrial emission databases was performed to assess data availability (Restiau et al., 2022). For stack emissions, Table 2 shows the main factors needed to produce reliable pollution dispersion calculations and population attributable exposure estimates. The production volume itself is not required for the population attributable exposure calculation but it can be used for predictive emission assessment and to understand whether emission factors are correlated to facility size.

Table 2. Main factors collected for stack emissions.

Parameter	Symbol [units]	Comments
Site location	°N, °W	Latitude and longitude; Relevant to specify population attributable exposure fraction.
Stack height	H , [m]	Actual stack height from the ground level. Mechanical plume rise increases the effective stack height by Δh (m).
Stack diameter	D , [m]	Stack exhaust inner diameter.
Gas exit velocity	V , [m/s]	Specifies the fluent flow exit velocity effecting on the mechanical plume rise and it is used to calculate fluent volume flow (m^3/s) and mass emission rate from concentration measurements.
Emission rate / Concentration	S , [g/s] / C , [mg/m^3]	Specifies the emission flow rate. This is calculated from reported annual emissions as annual average emission rate.
Composition of exhaust	$wt\%_i$, [%]	Weight fraction of pollutant i
Gas exit temperature	T , [°C]	Fluent temperature specifies the buoyancy when entering from the stack to the atmosphere. This effects on the mechanical plume rise.
Production volume	M , [tons/year]	Production volume can be used to calculate process efficacy and estimate the manufacturing process societal cost-benefits.

Population density at the emission source surroundings specifies the local scale human health impact. However, this information is not readily available and should be extracted from the facility's geographical location. In this range-finding study this was not performed.

The data availability was investigated from REACH dossiers, Pollutant Release and Transfer Register/European Environmental Agency (EMEP/EEA) air pollutant emission inventory guidebook 2019 (EEA, 2019a), North American pollutant release and transfer register (PRTR) Database (CEC, 2022), OECD database (OECD, 2022), Toxics Release Inventory (TRI) (US EPA, 2022), and the European-PRTR (E-PRTR) (EEA, 2022b). National emission databases were excluded from the assessment to avoid double counting.

2.2. AMBIENT AIR CONCENTRATION CALCULATION

A Gaussian plume model estimates the transport of the airborne pollutants from a point source by diffusion (due to turbulent eddy motion), advection (due to the wind) and removal by precipitation (Figure 2). The Gaussian plume model is a generally accepted method to calculate dispersion and deposition of pollutants from various sources (e.g., Stockie, 2011). In this study we used the bi-Gaussian plume model IMPACT (Immission Prognosis Air Concentration Tool), which is designed to calculate the industrial, residential, traffic and agricultural emissions impacts on the ground level air concentrations and depositions on a local scale (Flemish Government, 2018). IMPACT and its predecessor IDFM (Immission Frequency Distribution Model) have been tested and validated in numerous studies (Kretzschmar and Cosemans, 1996; Lefebvre et al., 2013; Lefebvre and Vranckx, 2013; Nikolova et al., 2011; Van Brusselen et al., 2016). The model uses the same algorithms as described in EEA "Guidance Report on preliminary assessment under EC Air Quality Directives" Annex 5.1 Urban dispersion model (EEA, 2016).

Figure 2. The basic concept of the Gaussian plume model for a point source: Source height H (m), emission flow rate Q (m^3/s), wind velocity \bar{u} (m/s).

The parameters used in the dispersion model include weather conditions (wind speed and direction, atmospheric stability, and ambient air temperature) and source parameters (source location and height, source type, gas exit velocity, exit temperature and chemical species mass flow rate). The model assumes constant meteorology in time and space. This limits the model use on hilly terrain, long distance predictions, and time resolution. The model predictability depends strongly on the emission source characterization, meteorological data representativeness and pollution deposition velocities (Giardina and Buffa, 2018). Meteorological data specify the plume rise behavior and direction, the atmospheric stability class, i.e., width of the gaussian plume shape, and the wet deposition. The IMPACT model parametrization is fully described in the user manual (Flemish Government, 2018).

A maximum receptor grid size was used, which is $40 \text{ km} \times 40 \text{ km}$. The factory was placed in the center of the receptor grid. The number of receptor points was 40,000, distributed equally within the modelling area (200 m distance between receptor points). A standard 1.5 m receptor height is used to calculate ground level concentrations. This represents "human inhalation exposure".

Meteorological measurement data sets are incorporated into IMPACT for default dispersion modeling. In this study, the meteorological data measured in Luchtbal, Antwerp, between 1/1/2007 and 31/12/2011 were used. Plume rise, Δh (m), from stack exit is inversely proportional to wind speed as $\Delta h \propto 1/u_{h_g}$, where u_{h_g} (m/s) is the wind speed at the source height h_g (m). A stack tip downwash occurs when the stack exit flow velocity, v (m/s) is low compared to the wind speed at the source height, u_{h_g} (m/s). The stack tip downwash is corrected when $v/u_{h_g} < 1.5$.

Dry deposition velocity can be estimated by using a surface layer resistance model (Giardina and Buffa, 2018). The deposition velocity depends on specific properties of the particles of the atmospheric structure, and of the deposition surface. Currently, there is no single accepted theoretical description of the dry deposition phenomena because of the deposition processes' complexity and the lack of experimental data covering all scenarios. Geometric mean diameter of the particles emitted from NFM processes range from PM_{2.5} (particle diameter < 2.5 μm) to coarse particles (e.g. González-Castanedo et al., 2014). The deposition velocity for particles in this particle size range vary from <0.01 to 20 cm/s depending on the deposition surface (Giardina and Buffa, 2018). Here was selected a geometric mean deposition velocity of 1 cm/s to estimate dry deposition velocity.

Wet deposition occurs at the time of precipitation and is relevant mainly for gaseous substances with high solubility (>1,000 mg/L). Modeling a wet deposition using a washout coefficient means that all the physical and chemical processes related to the pollutant removal are represented by one factor. Washout coefficient is dependent on a large number of parameters, such as rainfall rate, rain droplet size and aerosol size distributions and the concentrations (National Power and CERC, 2020). Here, a generally accepted conservative value of 0.0004 1/s is used to describe the wet deposition of highly soluble and volatile substances (Flemish Government, 2018; National Power and CERC, 2020).

Model sensitivity was tested by a) using EUSES parametrization with stack height 10 m, without plume rise and gas temperature 15 °C and b) by Antwerp meteorology from 2017.

2.3. EXPOSURE-RESPONSE FUNCTION FOR SELECTED POLLUTANT

The exposure-response functions (ERFs) and health endpoints with disability weights and durations used in this study are presented in Table 3. For the estimation of PM and NO_x related health burden was used a natural-cause mortality for adults. The baseline burden of death by natural causes (excluding injuries) is specified for ages 25+ while the PM_{2.5} and PM_{2.5-10} ERFs are typically evaluated for ages 30+ (Table 4). This can cause a small overestimation in PM natural cause DALYs. Unit risk DALY calculations are based on a lifetime exposure that is assigned for 70-year lifetime expectancy, which is lower than the life expectancy of 81.3 years used in this study. This can cause an underestimation of 1.16 in calculated DALYs based on unit risk.

One premature death in 2019 in Central Europe corresponded to 17.5 YLLs (Supplementary material 1, 2019 DALYs) which was applied both for year 2019 and 2020 DALY calculations. Another, a more general estimate for life loss by premature death, is given by COMEAP (2018) where a premature death statistical life loss corresponds to 12 years of lost life (i.e. 12 DALYs or 12 YLLs). COMEAP (2018) estimate was applied to calculate YLLs from studies reporting only the number of premature deaths.

Table 3. Summary of health endpoints and exposure-response functions. Abbreviations: UR = Unit Risk; RR = Relative Risk; ERF = Exposure Response Function; LCL = lower confidential limit; UCL = upper confidential limit; N/A = Not available. PM total DALYs were calculated by using bolded ERFs.

Pollutant	Health Endpoint	Age group	Type of ERF	ERF (LCL – UCL)	DALYs (Disability weight / duration)
PM_{2.5}	Natural-cause mortality (Chen and Hoek, 2020)	>30	RR, per 10 µg/m ³ increment	1.08 (1.06 - 1.09)	DALYs according to baseline disease burden (Table 4)
	Chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD) (Chen and Hoek, 2020)	All	RR, per 10 µg/m ³ increment	1.11 (1.05 - 1.17)	
	Ischemic heart disease (IHD) (Chen and Hoek, 2020)	All	RR, per 10 µg/m ³ increment	1.16 (1.10 - 1.21)	
	Respiratory diseases (Chen and Hoek, 2020)	All	RR, per 10 µg/m ³ increment	1.10 (1.03 - 1.18)	
	Acute lower respiratory infection (ALRI) (Chen and Hoek, 2020)	All	RR, per 10 µg/m ³ increment	1.16 (1.01- 1.34)	
	Cerebrovascular diseases (stroke) (Chen and Hoek, 2020)	All	RR, per 10 µg/m ³ increment	1.11 (1.04 - 1.18)	
	Restricted activity days (RAD) (Hurley et al., 2005)	15-64	UR, per 1 µg/m ³ increment	0.09 (0.079-1.013)	0.0027 DALYs (0.099 / 0.00274-y) (Hänninen and Knol, 2011)
PM_{2.5-10}	Natural-cause mortality (Chen and Hoek, 2020)	>30	RR, per 10 µg/m ³ increment	1.04 (1.03 - 1.06)	DALYs according to baseline disease burden (Table 4)
	COPD (Chen and Hoek, 2020)	All	RR, per 10 µg/m ³ increment	1.19 (0.95 - 1.49)	
	IHD (Chen and Hoek, 2020)	All	RR, per 10 µg/m ³ increment	1.06 (1.01 - 1.10)	
	Respiratory diseases (Chen and Hoek, 2020)	All	RR, per 10 µg/m ³ increment	1.12 (1.06 - 1.19)	
	ALRI (Chen and Hoek, 2020)	All	RR, per 10 µg/m ³ increment	- (None)	
	Cerebrovascular diseases (stroke) (Chen and Hoek, 2020)	All	RR, per 10 µg/m ³ increment	1.01 (0.83 - 1.21)	
	Lower respiratory symptoms (LRS) days for school children (Hurley et al., 2005)	5-14 (here all <15)	UR, per 1 µg/m ³ increment	0.186 (0.186-0.277)	0.0027 DALYs (0.099 / 0.00274-y) (Hänninen and Knol, 2011)

	LRS days for adults (Hurley et al., 2005)	>15	UR, per 1 µg/m ³ increment	0.13 (0.015-0.243)	0.7645 DALYs (0.279 / 0.00274-y) (Hänninen and Knol, 2011)
SO₂	Lung cancer (Nafstad, 2003)	All	RR, per 10 µg/m ³ increment	1.01 (0.94-1.08)	DALYs according to baseline disease burden (Table 4)
NO_x	Natural-cause mortality (Huangfu and Atkinson, 2020)	>30	HR, per 20 µg/m ³ increment	1.02 (95% CI 1.00-1.04)	
CO	IHD (Hosseinpoor et al., 2005)	All	RR per 1000 µg/m ³ increment	1.00934 (1.01512-1.00359)	
Ni	Lung Cancer (Bickel and Friedrich, 2005)	All	UR, per 1 µg/m ³ increment	2.4×10 ⁻⁴ (1.1×10 ⁻⁵ -2.4×10 ⁻⁴)	21.8 DALYs (Global Burden of Disease 2019 Cancer Collaboration, 2022)
Cr (as Cr^{VI})	Lung cancer (Proctor et al., 2016)	All	UR, per 1 µg/m ³ increment	8.32×10 ⁻³ (3.59×10 ⁻³ -1.74×10 ⁻²)	
Cd	Lung Cancer (Bickel and Friedrich, 2005; Takenaka et al., 1983)	All	UR, per 1 µg/m ³ increment	1.8×10 ⁻³ (1.0×10 ⁻³ -1.8×10 ⁻³)	
As	Lung Cancer (Erraguntla et al., 2012)	All	UR, per 1 µg/m ³ increment	1.5×10 ⁻⁴ (N/A)	
Pb	Specific, see Appendix: DALY calculations				
C₆H₆	Leukemia (Hänninen and Knol, 2011)	All	UR, cancers per µg/m ³ increment (see below)	6.0×10 ⁻⁶ (2.26×10 ⁻⁶ - 7.8×10 ⁻⁶)	
Benzo(a)pyrene (BaP)	Lung cancer (WHO, 2000)	All	UR, cancers per ng/m ³ increment (see below)	8.7×10 ⁻⁵ (N/A)	
Dioxin	Total cancer incidence (Hänninen and Knol, 2011)	All	UR, cancers per pg/kg/d increment (see below)	1×10 ⁻³ (0.57×10 ⁻³ - 5.1×10 ⁻³)	
Naphthalene	Cancer (US EPA, 2021)	All	UR, cancers per 1 µg/m ³ increment	3.4×10 ⁻³ (N/A)	
Polychlorinated biphenyls (PCBs)	Cancer (US-EPA, 2022)	All	UR, cancers per 1 µg/m ³ increment	0.1×10 ⁻³ (N/A)	
Tetrachloroethylene	Cancer (US-EPA, 2022)	All	UR, cancers per 1 µg/m ³ increment	2.60×10 ⁻⁷ (N/A)	
Trichloroethylene (TRI)	Cancer (US-EPA, 2022)	All	UR, cancers per 1 µg/m ³ increment	4.10×10 ⁻⁶ (N/A)	
Dichloromethane (DCM)	Hepatic, respiratory cancer (US EPA, 2011)	All	UR, cancers per 1 µg/m ³ increment	4.10×10 ⁻⁸ (N/A)	

V (as V ₂ O ₅)*	Inhalation exposure response functions N/A (MacGregor et al., 2020)	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
Ba*	Inhalation exposure response functions N/A (ATSDR, 2007)	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
Ag*	Inhalation exposure response functions N/A (US EPA, 1991)	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
Sr*	Inhalation exposure response functions N/A (ATSDR, 2004)	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
Hg*	Inhalation exposure response functions N/A (Hu et al., 2021)	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
Cu*	Inhalation exposure response functions N/A (Taylor et al., 2020)	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
Zn*	Inhalation exposure response functions N/A (US EPA, 2005)	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A

*Only metals are listed, see full list of substances without ERFs from Supplementary Material 1.

Table 4. Baseline disease burden as DALYs per 100 000 persons for Central Europe, both sex, and year 2019 with average value and upper and lower confidence intervals (Global Burden of Disease Collaborative Network, 2020). The average values are applied both for year 2019 and 2020 DALY calculations.

Cause name	Age	Average	LCL	UCL
Natural-cause mortality without injuries	25+	40737	36054	45573
TBL lung cancer	All	1665	1460	1903
Ischemic heart disease (IHD)	All	4790	4217	5372
Chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD)	All	824	735	916
Lower respiratory infections (ALRI)	All	525	463	585
Cerebrovascular diseases (stroke)	All	3229	2833	3602
Chronic respiratory diseases (respiratory diseases)	All	3229	2833	3602

2.4. POPULATION DENSITY AND EXPOSURE ESTIMATION

Statistical population factors were selected from the year 2019 which were not impacted by COVID-19. Population density was set to 500 persons/km² which corresponds to densely populated European countries, such as the Netherlands (Eurostat, 2019). Life expectancy at birth in the EU was 81.3 years in 2019 as an average for both sex (Eurostat, 2022a). Age distribution in 2019 was as follows: <15-y 15%, 15-29-y 17%, and >65-y 17% (Eurostat, 2022b) (Supplementary material 1: Population). Because ERFs have a linear relation and population density was set to constant, the exposure concentration was estimated by using the average concentration.

2.5. DALY CALCULATION

Air pollution health risk assessment methods have been well established in Europe during past two decades (Héroux et al., 2015) and adopted in many global (e.g. Anenberg et al., 2019; Vohra et al., 2021) and local (e.g. Holnicki et al., 2017; Koivisto et al., 2022; Tainio, 2015) projects, including the Global Burden of Disease (GBD) studies (e.g. Murray et al., 2020). Hänninen and Knol (2011) presents methods for estimating burden of disease related to environmental risks: how to derive the population attributable fraction using a relative risk (RR; Method 1 in Hänninen and Knol, 2011) or a unit risk (Method 2 in Hänninen and Knol, 2011) and in whether disease burdens are derived from the baseline burden of disease or estimated using disability weights (DW) and duration factors (L). Details of the DALY calculations are given in Appendix and Figure 3 shows an example of the calculation methods.

DALY calculations were performed without discounting or age weighting, meaning that health impacts occurring later in the future are counted with similar weight as immediate effects, health effects are weighted the same at all ages and no lag times are included (Hänninen and Knol, 2011; Murray et al., 2012). Here, possible concentration threshold values were not included and potential double counting of the burden between the pollutants was not considered (favors higher DALYs). For example, NO₂ long term effects may overlap with particle health effects up to 33% (Lehtomäki et al., 2018). To avoid double-counting with the other diseases, the burden due to chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD), ischemic heart disease (IHD), restricted activity days (RAD), acute lower respiratory infection (ALRI), respiratory diseases and stroke were not included in the overall NO_x and PM burden.

A) Relative risk approach

Example PM2.5 Natural-cause mortality in 2019
 $RR = 1.08$ per $10 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ increment

$$RR_u = 1.08^{\frac{1}{10}} = 1.00773$$

$$RR^E = RR_u^{0.193} = 1.0015$$

$$PAF = \frac{(RR^E - 1)}{(RR^E - 1) + 1} = 0.0015$$

$$DALY = PAF \times 40738 \frac{DALY}{10^5\ persons} \times 8 \times 10^5\ persons \approx 330\ DALY$$

B) Unit risk approach for lung cancer

Example for As lung cancers in 2019
 $UR = 1.5 \times 10^{-4}$ lung cancer per $1 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ increment

$$AI = 1.2 \times 10^{-4} \times UR \times 8 \times 10^5 = 0.014\ \text{lung cancers}$$

$$DALY = \frac{AI}{81.3\ \text{years}} \times 21.8\ \text{DALY per lung cancer} \approx 0.004\ \text{DALY per year}$$

Figure 3. Example of DALY calculation by using A) relative risk for natural-cause mortality and B) unit risk for lung cancer.

3. RESULTS

3.1. INDUSTRIAL EMISSION DATA COLLECTION FROM E-PRTR

A full report of the emission inventory evaluation is given by Restiau et al. (2022). A summary of the ‘data availability’ is given in Table 5. For the European industry, there was no information available for fugitive emissions, which hence were exempted from this evaluation. Population density around the facility can be extracted from the site location data but this requires a systematic approach which was not the focus in this project. Based on the data availability (Table 5), the E-PRTR database was selected as the source for NFM-industry emissions.

The E-PRTR, as well as other databases, does not separate emissions if different materials are produced. Thus, the emission impacts cannot be associated with individual metal production or application and potential factory emissions related to other than NFM sector activities are not separated here from NFM-industry emissions.

Table 5. A summary of emission data availability from the different databases. Color coding is green = available, orange = available for some data, red = unavailable.

parameter	REACH dossier	EMEP /EEA	North American PRTR	OECD	TRI	E-PRTR
Site location	Red	Red	Green	Country/region	Green	Green
Stack height	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Yellow
Stack diameter	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red
Gas exit velocity	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red
Gas exit temperature	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red
Emission	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green
Composition of exhaust	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red
Production volume	Red	Red	Red	Red	Production ratio	Yellow
Fugitive emission	Red	Red	Red	Red	Green	Red

For the NFM industry, the following reporting thresholds have been set by EC (2009) Directives 91/689/EEC and 96/61/EC (E-PRTR Annex I Main Activity Code):

- 2(e)(i) For the production of non-ferrous crude metals from ore, concentrates or secondary raw materials by metallurgical, chemical or electrolytic processes: All facilities are subjected to reporting.
- 2(e)(ii) For the smelting, including the alloying, of non-ferrous metals, including recovered products (refining, foundry casting, etc.): With a melting capacity of 4 tonnes per day for lead and cadmium or 20 tonnes per day for all other metals.
- 2(f) Installations for surface treatment of metals and plastic materials using an electrolytic or chemical process: Where the volume of the treatment vats equals 30 m³.

For the main health impact assessment, the 2020 emissions extracted from the E-PRTR database were used (Supplementary material 1: E-PRTR 2020). However, due to potential impact of COVID-19 lockdowns and supply chain disruptions in Europe to production volumes, the impact of 2019 emissions were also evaluated (Supplementary material 1: E-PRTR 2019).

For the years 2019 and 2020 were reported 371 and 283 emission measurements based on 106 and 69 facilities, respectively. Stack height was reported in 29 emission measurements by 7 facilities which varied from 14 to 160 m. One facility reported processing volumes which was not sufficient for cost-benefit assessment. Exhaust fluent particle size information was not available. The data distribution according to E-PRTR activity categories were:

- 2(e)(i): 193 emission measurements from 48 facilities.
- 2(e)(ii): 90 emission measurements from 21 facilities.
- 2(f): No emission data reported for years 2019 and 2020.

3.2. AMBIENT AIR CONCENTRATION AND POPULATION EXPOSURE

The assessment of individual factory emissions was not performed due to the limited data availability. Thus, a default factory and environmental parameters, such as meteorology, population local distribution and age were specified with default values. This approach is adequate, because in this study, the exposure response functions have a log-linear relation with concentrations (Pope et al., 2015). Thus, the DALYs summed from individual factory assessment equal to DALYs calculated for emission from a single stack with emission rate of total emissions.

According to E-PRTR, in 2019 the NFM-industry emissions, excluding CO₂ emissions of 24×10⁶ tons and methane emissions of 2259 tons, represented 5.10×10⁵ tons consisting of 88.4% CO, 5.7% NO_x, 3.9% SO_x, 1.2% non-methane volatile organic compounds (NMVOC) and 0.9% of other pollutants (Table 6). Similarly, in 2020 the NFM-industry emissions, excluding CO₂ emissions of 43×10⁶ tons and methane emissions of 4518 tons, represented 5.45×10⁵ tons consisting of 89.5% CO, 6.8% NO_x, 2.1% SO_x, 1.1% NMVOC and 0.5% of other pollutants (Table 6).

The NFM-sector emissions were described as aggregated emissions and by using statistical stack properties measured for NFM metal smelting ($n = 412$) and rolling ($n = 280$) in 10 German Federal States for the years 1996/1994 (Pregger and Friedrich, 2009). Following emission weighted averages were used: stack height ($h = 53$ m), inner diameter ($D = 1.03$ m), flue exit velocity (5.9 m/s) and gas temperature (218.5 °C). Emission rate (g/s) was calculated by dividing annual emissions with seconds in a year and assuming continuous emissions through the year.

IMPACT dispersion modeling was performed by using a 40 km by 40 km modeling grid where the aggregated stack (height 53 m) was positioned at center of the grid start (Figure 4). IMPACT simulation reports are given in Supplementary material 2, IMPACT reports. Concentrations of individual pollutants were calculated by

assuming that the concentration composition is the same as reported, *i.e.*, total concentration was multiplied with the fraction of each pollutant to obtain concentration of the specific component.

Figure 4. An example of annual average total ground level concentrations for aggregated NFM-industrial emissions for year 2019 (16159 g/sec, continuous emissions) calculated by using IMPACT. Stack is located at the center of the plot. Numbers represent the concentration range in µg/m³. Original figure with receptor point concentrations is provided in Supplementary material 1, 2019 IMPACT Conc.

Average concentrations of the NFM emissions in the model area were 69.7 and 74.6 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ respectively for years 2019 and 2020 (Table 7). Average concentration at the model edges was on average 24.3 and 26.0 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$, respectively for years 2019 and 2020. This shows that the population exposure assessment was not complete in the model area and the air emission health impact assessment is only partially covered outside the current model region. Calculated concentrations are given in Supplementary material 1: 2019 Conc and 2020 Conc.

3.3. DALY CALCULATION

DALYs of the NFM-industry emissions were calculated at local scale (40 by 40 km^2 area) for each pollutant and health endpoint in 2019 and 2020 for which ERFs were available (Table 7). Total DALYs for the year 2019 and 2020 emissions were 1429.6 and 1445.9, respectively. Major cause for DALYs were (Figure 5):

- 2019 emissions: NO_x (868 DALYs) and $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ and $\text{PM}_{2.5-10}$ (501 DALYs) covering 95.8% of total DALYs.
- 2020 emissions: NO_x (1113 DALYs) and $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ and $\text{PM}_{2.5-10}$ (287 DALYs) covering 96.8% of total DALYs.

Other relevant pollutants for the health impact were (as an average of 2020 and 2019 emissions) SO_x (28.3 DALY), CO (24.5 DALYs), and naphthalene (2.9 DALYs) while others were on average below 1 DALY. Metals, namely Ni, Cr(VI), Cd, As and Pb, contribution to DALYs were below 0.015%. Natural-cause mortality was caused 66.3% by YLLs and 33.7% by YLDs (Supplementary material 1: 2019 DALYs). Disease specific causes for $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ DALYs were IHD and stroke while for $\text{PM}_{2.5-10}$ it was IHD, COPD and stroke (Table 7). Regardless the emissions were 7% lower in 2019 than in 2020, the DALYs were similar. DALYs by $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ and $\text{PM}_{2.5-10}$ emissions were ca. 2 times higher in 2019 than in 2020 while NO_x DALYs was 244.9 DALYs lower in 2019 than in 2020 (Table 7). DALY rates for the model population were 179 and 181 DALYs per 100,000 persons (DALYs/ 10^5) for the years 2019 and 2020, respectively.

Figure 5. DALYs by emission substances for A) 2019 and B) 2020.

Table 6. Aggregated emissions for NFM industry extracted from E-PRTR for 2(e)(i), 2(e)(ii) and 2(e) activity categories. Particle emissions are reported in E-PRTR as PM₁₀. Here it was assumed that PM₁₀ contains 50% PM_{2.5}. Abundant pollutants with fraction >1% from total emissions are bolded.

Pollutant	2019 NFM emissions		2020 NFM emissions	
	Emission, [kg]	Fraction, [%]	Emission, [kg]	Fraction, [%]
PM _{2.5}	1414139	0.28	807140	0.15
PM ₁₀	1414139	0.28	807140	0.15
Sulphur oxides (SO_x)	19626294	3.85	11631970	2.14
Nitrogen oxides (NO_x)	28998945	5.69	37145030	6.82
Carbon monoxide (CO)	450342365	88.38	487134186	89.5
Nickel and compounds (as Ni)	9549	0.0019	7557.3	0.0014
Cobalt	ND	ND	ND	ND
Antimony (as Sb trioxide)	ND	ND	ND	ND
Chromium and compounds (as Cr), 2% is assumed to be Cr(VI) (Krystek et al 2007)	9028	0.0018	5655	0.001
Cadmium and compounds (as Cd)	1747	0.3×10 ⁻³	914.2	0.2×10 ⁻³
Arsenic and compounds (as As)	872	0.2×10 ⁻³	350	0.1×10 ⁻³
Lead and compounds (as Pb)	30258	0.0059	31615	0.006
Benzene C ₆ H ₆	74420	0.015	144960	0.027
Benzo(a)pyrene	ND	ND	ND	ND
PCDD + PCDF (dioxins + furans) (as Teq) Here as dioxine	0.25	6.9×10 ⁻⁹	0.050542	9.3×10 ⁻⁹
Naphthalene	33637	0.0066	8550	0.0016
Polychlorinated biphenyls (PCBs)	1	25.9×10 ⁻⁶	0.718	0.14×10 ⁻⁶
Tetrachloroethylene	3000	0.6×10 ⁻³	6640	0.0012
Trichloroethylene (TRI)	32790	0.0064	103500	0.019
Mercury and compounds (as Hg)	730	1.4×10 ⁻³	1802	0.3×10 ⁻³
Non-methane volatile organic compounds (NMVOC)	6012340	1.18	6058370	1.11
Benzo(g,h,i)perylene	0	4.9×10 ⁻⁸	135	24.8×10 ⁻⁶
Chlorine and inorganic compounds (as HCl)	765600	0.15	94900	0.017
Copper and compounds (as Cu)	10182	0.0020	5363	0.001
Fluorine and inorganic compounds (as HF)	248200	0.0058	108800	0.020
Hydrochlorofluorocarbons (HCFCs)	3950	0.8×10 ⁻³	168	30.9×10 ⁻⁶
Hydro-fluorocarbons (HFCS)	2597	0.5×10 ⁻³	4270	0.0008
Nitrous oxide (N ₂ O)	106400	0.021	335800	0.062
Pentachlorobenzene	ND	ND	107	19.6×10 ⁻⁶
Perfluorocarbons (PFCs)	3514	0.7×10 ⁻³	12210	0.002
Polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs)	4413	0.9×10 ⁻³	17869	0.003
Sulphur hexafluoride (SF ₆)	4771	0.9×10 ⁻³	1329	0.2×10 ⁻³
Zinc and compounds (as Zn)	95608	0.019	63703	0.012
Hydrogen cyanide (HCN)	296062	0.058	2093	0.4×10 ⁻³
Chlorofluorocarbons (CFCs)	2110	0.4×10 ⁻³	ND	ND
Dichloromethane (DCM)	18400	0.0036	ND	ND
Ammonia	10500	0.0021	ND	ND
Emission sum, [kg/year]		509576563		544542127

Table 7. Annual average ground level concentration within the model area (40 km × 40 km) and respective DALYs for the default population of 800 000 (500 persons/km²).

Pollutant	Cause	NFM-industry 2019		NFM-industry 2020	
		Concentration, [µg/m ³]	DALYs	Concentration, [µg/m ³]	DALYs
PM _{2.5} (50% of PM ₁₀)	Natural-cause mortality	0.19	329.5	0.11	188.4
	COPD		13.3		7.6
	IHD		109.8		62.8
	Respiratory diseases		16.0		9.1
	ALRI		12.0		6.9
	Stroke		52.1		29.8
	RAD		2.57		1.47
PM _{2.5-10} (50% of PM ₁₀)	Natural-cause mortality	0.19	168.0	0.11	96.0
	COPD		22.1		12.7
	IHD		43.2		24.7
	Respiratory diseases		19.0		10.9
	Stroke		5.0		2.8
	LRS school children		1.2		0.67
	LRS adults		4.6		2.65
Sulphur oxides (SO _x)	Lung cancer	2.68	35.5	1.59	21.1
Nitrogen oxides (NO _x)	Natural-cause mortality	3.97	868.4	5.09	1113.3
Carbon monoxide (CO)	IHD	61.58	23.5	66.7	25.4
Nickel and compounds (as Ni)	Cancer	0.0013	0.065	0.001	0.051
Cobalt	Cancer	ND	ND	ND	ND
Antimony (as Sb trioxide)	Cancer	ND	ND	ND	ND
Chromium and compounds (as Cr), 2% is assumed to be Cr(VI) (Krystek et al 2007)	Cancer	0.0012 (Cr(VI) 2.5×10 ⁻⁵)	0.042	0.00077 (Cr(VI) 1.55×10 ⁻⁵)	0.027
Cadmium and compounds (as Cd)	Cancer	0.00024	0.089	0.13×10 ⁻³	0.046
Arsenic and compounds (as As)	Cancer	0.00012	0.0037	4.8×10 ⁻⁵	0.0015
Lead and compounds (as Pb)	Specific	0.0041	0.015	0.004	0.016
Benzene C ₆ H ₆	Cancer	0.010	0.013	0.020	0.025
Benzo(a)pyrene	Cancer	ND	ND	ND	ND
PCDD + PCDF (dioxins + furans) (as Teq) Here as dioxine	Cancer	4.8×10 ⁻⁹	0.99×10 ⁻⁶	6.9×10 ⁻⁹	1.4×10 ⁻⁶
Naphthalene	Cancer	0.0046	3.2	0.0012	0.82
Polychlorinated biphenyls (PCBs)	Cancer	1.8×10 ⁻⁷	0.0085	9.8×10 ⁻⁸	0.019
Tetrachloroethylene	Cancer	0.0004	0.00024	0.91×10 ⁻³	0.00076
Trichloroethylene (TRI)	Cancer	0.0045	8.4×10 ⁻⁵	0.014	0.00021
Mercury and compounds (as Hg)	N/A	0.00010	N/A	0.25×10 ⁻³	N/A
Non-methane volatile organic compounds (NMVOC)	N/A	0.82	N/A	0.83	N/A
Benzo(g,h,i)perylene	N/A	3.4×10 ⁻⁸	N/A	1.9×10 ⁻⁵	N/A
Chlorine and inorganic compounds (as HCl)	N/A	0.10	N/A	0.013	N/A
Copper and compounds (as Cu)	N/A	0.0014	N/A	0.73×10 ⁻³	N/A
Fluorine and inorganic compounds (as HF)	N/A	0.034	N/A	0.015	N/A

Hydrochlorofluorocarbons (HCFCs)	N/A	0.00054	N/A	0.23×10^{-5}	N/A
Hydro-fluorocarbons (HFCS)	N/A	0.00036	N/A	0.59×10^{-3}	N/A
Nitrous oxide (N ₂ O)	N/A	0.015	N/A	0.046	N/A
Pentachlorobenzene	N/A	ND	ND	1.5×10^{-5}	N/A
Perfluorocarbons (PFCs)	N/A	0.00048	N/A	0.0017	N/A
Polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs)	N/A	0.00060	N/A	0.0025	N/A
Sulphur hexafluoride (SF ₆)	N/A	0.00065	N/A	0.19×10^{-3}	N/A
Zinc and compounds (as Zn)	N/A	0.013	N/A	0.0087	N/A
Hydrogen cyanide (HCN)	N/A	0.040	N/A	0.29×10^{-3}	N/A
Chlorofluorocarbons (CFCs)	N/A	0.00029	N/A	ND	ND
Dichloromethane (DCM)	N/A	0.0025	2.96×10^{-6}	ND	ND
Ammonia	Cancer	0.0014	N/A	ND	ND
Total concentration		69.68 µg/m³		74.56 µg/m³	
DALY PM_{2.5}+PM_{2.5-10} (nat.-cause mortality + LRS school children)		500		290	
DALY metals		0.21		0.14	
DALY others		928.0		1159.1	
Total DALYs		1429.6		1445.9	

3.4. SENSITIVITY TEST

A simple sensitivity test was performed by using EUSES stack properties where stack height is 10 m, plume rise is disabled and ignoring mechanical plume rise by setting exhaust fluent temperature at 15 °C. This would increase the average ground level concentration to 252 µg/m³ and the concentration at the model edges to 45 µg/m³. The effect of meteorology was tested by using Antwerp meteorology data from 2017. This did not change the average ground level concentration notably. The results can be seen from the IMPACT report files (Supplementary material 2, IMPACT reports).

4. DISCUSSION

4.1. PRECAUTIONARY LEVEL AND QUALITY OF THE ASSESSMENT

The evaluation was based on stack emissions because fugitive emissions are not collected at the level of E-PRTR. Fugitive emissions are related to low level point, line, and area sources increasing concentrations at local scale (Ontario, 2022).

Here, the chimney was parameterized with emission weighted averages. Stack height was set at 53 m while according to E-PRTR the height ranged from 14 to 160 m. Emissions from high stacks are generally higher to minimize their health impacts. Thus, the averaging performed here increases high stack emissions contribution to ground level concentrations while low stack emissions contribution is reduced. As a sum, the ground level concentrations are expected to be overestimated.

A precautionary DALY assessment was performed without discounting or age-weighting on DALYs, use of cut-off concentration, delayed health effects, or potential DALY double counting due to NO_x and PM health effects overlap (WHO, 2013). NO₂ cut-off concentration 20 µg/m³ is typically applied and 20 µg/m³ value is recommended by Héroux et al. (2015). EEA has recognized the NO₂ cut-off concentration problematic because health outcomes are associated at NO₂ exposure levels of 10 µg/m³ (Raaschou-Nielsen et al., 2012). The simulated average NO_x of 5.09 µg/m³ (max 48.5 µg/m³) and if 10 µg/m³ cut-off concentration is considered, year 2020 NO_x DALYs would reduce by 72% to 307 DALYs. It is estimated that NO₂ health effects might overlap up to 33% with PM_{2.5}. To avoid double counting, EEA reports the health impacts separately for the three pollutants (PM_{2.5}, NO₂ and O₃) as this may lead to double counting of people who are exposed to high

levels of more than one pollutant (EEA, 2020). Correcting here the double counting the number of DALYs would reduce the year 2020 NO_x DALYs by 367. Both cut-off concentration of 10 µg/m³ and double counting would reduce the year 2020 NO_x DALYs to 206 (now 1113 DALYs by NO_x).

In this exercise, DALY count is directly proportional to population which was set to 800,000 corresponding to a population density of 500 persons/km². In Central Europe, population densities on a country level vary from 106 to 507 persons/km² (Eurostat, 2019). On average in the EU, the population density is 109 persons/km² and the population density was considered here as a precautionary value.

ERFs mean values were used instead of upper confidence limits to obtain an objective picture of the DALY burden. Lead DALYs were calculated by using a simplified approach and mercury DALYs were not calculated because ERFs were not directly applicable (Hu et al., 2021). Only major health endpoints for PM were investigated without a systematic review, such as PM exposure related asthma (Jacquemin et al., 2015; Khreis et al., 2017), coronary heart disease (Cesaroni et al., 2014), dementia (Wang et al., 2020) and diabetes (Eze et al., 2015) were not evaluated. However, these DALYs are included in the PM DALYs via natural-cause DALY burden.

Recently derived ERFs for PM_{2.5} and PM_{2.5-10} were used (Chen and Hoek, 2020). For the PM_{2.5} natural-cause mortality was used an ERF of 1.08 per 10 µg/m³ PM_{2.5} increase, which is slightly higher than commonly applied factor of 1.062 per 10 µg/m³ PM_{2.5} increase (see also Pope et al., 2020). Overall, the health endpoints covered in this study were similar as in other air pollution BoD assessment studies (e.g., (EEA, 2019b; Holnicki et al., 2017; Juginović et al., 2021; Kushta et al., 2021; Lehtomäki et al., 2018; Schucht et al., 2021; Tainio, 2015; Tarín-Carrasco et al., 2022; Trinomics, 2022).

All DALYs were not counted by the 40 km by 40 km model because the model area is local and does not fully cover the population exposure fraction. On average, calculated average concentration on the model edges was ca. 25 µg/m³, and thus, a relevant fraction of DALYs was not captured. A full scale emission impact assessment requires global scale dispersion models, such as GEOS-Chem (see e.g., Anenberg et al., 2019; Vohra et al., 2021). It is not possible to give an estimate of how global scale exposure assessment effect on the DALYs as compared to the local scale model applied in this study.

4.2. BENEFITS OF ZERO-EMISSIONS

At local scale, the NFM-industry emissions average burden of disease was ca. 1,440 DALYs per year. The most effective way to reduce DALYs by direct inhalation exposure by NFM-industry is to reduce NO_x and PM emissions as they cover ca. 96% of the total DALYs. Metals contribution to DALYs was insignificant (<0.015%) which is a common observation (e.g., Hänninen and Knol, 2011; Holnicki et al., 2017; Lehtomäki et al., 2016; Li et al., 2020; Schucht et al., 2021).

EEA (2021a) estimated that in 2019, approximately 307,000 premature deaths were attributable to PM_{2.5} in the EU-27 Member States. Nitrogen dioxide (NO₂) was linked to 40,400 premature deaths, and ground-level ozone was linked to 16,800 premature deaths. YLLs related to premature deaths (1 YLL = 1 DALY assuming YLD is zero) attributable to PM_{2.5}, NO₂ and O₃ exposure in the EU-27, 2019 were 3,370,000, 512,800 and 215,100, respectively (EEA, 2021b). In Central European countries, air pollution cause from ca. 400 (Switzerland) to 1,290 (Poland) YLL per 100,000 habitants (EEA, 2021a). NFM-industry burden of disease including both YLDs and YLLs at local scale is ca. 0.04% of YLL by PM_{2.5} pollution in EU-27. Assuming an ideal situation where NFM emission reductions do not produce additional burden for air pollution e.g., via increased energy consumption, the NFM emissions at local scale does not make significant contribution to overall YLL in EU-27.

DALY and DALY rate comparison is not straightforward because the exposure model population density may vary significantly (e.g., assessment performed only at the hotspot or at whole country levels). Baseline burden disease rates depend strongly on the location. The average disease burden rates for Central Europe used in this study may not represent the baseline disease burden rates where the actual NFM-factories locate. Other challenges may cause non-linear ERFs, different cut-off values, double counting, different health endpoints, lack of some relevant pollutant components and uncertainties in ground level concentration calculations (e.g., hilly terrains).

Here were also collected the main results for some BoD studies to compare NFM industry emission impacts with other sectors (Table 8). The NFM-sector average annual DALYs were 1,440 and the DALY rate was *ca.* 180 DALYs/10⁵ (1.0 DALYs per factory/10⁵). NFM-industry DALY rates or DALYs were from 0.05 to 4.2 times the DALY rates or DALYs reported in Table 8 BoD studies. It is good to note that the impact assessment was performed for all NFM-sector emissions as reported in E-PRTR while Table 8 mainly contains only a fraction of the emission sector as specified by EEA (2021c). For example, traffic emission impacts at a country level are in the range of 150 DALY/10⁵ while on a city level it ranges from 272 YLL/10⁵ (Malmö, SE) to 1,470 DALY/10⁵ (Warsaw, PL). This is because the ratios are higher in densely populated areas than at country level including persons with negligible exposure levels. Similarly, here NFM-industry DALY rate is calculated at local scale where it is higher than at large scale including persons with potentially negligible exposure to the NFM emissions.

The model area was 40 km by 40 km which corresponds to 1,600 km². Warsaw area is 500 km² which fit in the model area. The NFM-industry DALYs for Warsaw population of 1.7 million would be *ca.* 2,900 DALYs per year. This is *ca.* 10 times less than DALYs by Warsaw public transportation in 2010. This gives some estimate of NFM-industry impact on a local scale where all NFM factories are in one city. It is good to remind that fugitive emissions are excluded from the NFM-industry assessment.

Holnicki et al. (2017) estimated the health impact of following source categories in Warsaw in 2012 consisting of:

- High point sources (24)—energy generation;
- Low point sources (3,880)—industrial plants;
- Area sources (6,962)—residential combustion;
- Line sources (7,285)—urban road traffic;
- Boundary conditions (the inflow of some pollutants due to the regional/national level emission based on the results from the European scale EMEP model).

The annual health loss by air pollution was related to the inflow of air pollution from outside the municipality borders (70.6 death/10⁵), air pollution emitted within the administrative borders of the municipality (63.6 death/10⁵), households (40 death/10⁵), transport (22 death/10⁵), and industry (1 death/10⁵). Air pollution inflow from outside or within the Warsaw region was a major cause for premature deaths, followed by households and transport. Local industry did not have a significant contribution to the Warsaw air pollution health impact.

This demonstrates that global modeling is needed to understand better NFM-industry emissions overall health burden. Local emission impact assessment suggests that the health impact of NFM-industry sector is not as relevant as other emission sectors *e.g.*, by households and road traffic. Figure 6 shows that NFM-industry emissions are not high compared to other key emission categories.

Table 8. Ambient air pollution health burden by different emission sectors. Premature death is assumed to correspond 12 years of lost life (*i.e.* 12 DALYs or 12 YLLs) as specified in COMEAP (2018) for statistical life loss by premature death. This is slightly lower than for Central Europe (average 17.5 YLL/death). Ratio of NFM-DALY/Study-DALY <1 indicates NFM impact is smaller than in the study (calculated by using DALY ratios, if possible).

Scenario	Study / studied pollutants	Location (Date) / population	Health burden	DALYs/YLLs per 100 000 persons	NFM-DALY/Study-DALY
Transport	Tainio (2015) / PM, NO _x , SO ₂ , BaP, Cd, Pb, Ni	Warsaw, PL (2010) / 1.7 million (3287 persons/km ²)	25 000 DALYs per year (79% PM, 20% NO _x , 0.8% Pb, 0.2% other: BaP, Cd, Ni)	1 470 DALY/10 ⁵	0.12
	Anenberg et al. (2019) Includes international shipping and non-road mobile	France (2015) / 66.55 million	6 400 deaths	117.6 YLL/10 ⁵	1.53
		Germany (2015) / 81.69 million	13 000 deaths; 15.9 deaths/10 ⁵	190.8 YLL/10 ⁵	0.94
		Italy (2015) / 60.73 million	78 00 deaths; 12.8 deaths/10 ⁵	153.6 YLL/10 ⁵	1.17

	sources / PM _{2.5} , O ₃	Other EU (2015) / 508.2 million	22 000 deaths; 9.5 deaths/10 ⁵	114 YLL/10 ⁵	1.58
	Malmqvist et al. (2018) / PM _{2.5} , NO _x	Malmö, SE (2016) / 326 100 (4050 persons/km ²)	55 to 93 deaths	272 YLL/10 ⁵	0.66
	Mueller et al. (2017) / PM _{2.5}	Barcelona, ES (2012) / 1.36 million	9901 DALYs	729.3 DALYs/10 ⁵	0.25
Residential wood combustion	Orru et al. (2022) / PM _{2.5}	Helsinki, FI (2013); Oslo, NO (2013); Umeå, SE (2011); Copenhagen, DK (2014) / 1.88 million in total	4 248 YLL per year	226 YLL/10 ⁵	0.80
	Savolahti et al. (2019) / PM _{2.5}	Finland (2015) / 5.48 million	3 400 DALYs and 200 deaths	106.4 DALYs/10 ⁵	1.69
	Sarigiannis et al. (2015) / PM	Thessaloniki, GR (winter 2012-2013) / 0.81 million	3 540 YLL	427 YLL/10 ⁵	0.42
Fossil fuel combustion in power generation, industry, ships, aircraft, ground transportation, backup generators, kerosene, oil/gas extraction	Vohra et al. (2021) / PM _{2.5}	Europe (2012) / 505.7 million	1 447 000 deaths (Exceeds the premature deaths in the EU because ERF is different than used by the EEA; Vodonos et al., 2018)	3 434 YLL/10 ⁵	0.05
Large pig farms (>1000 heads of sows or fattening pigs)	Costantini et al. (2020) / PM	Europe / N/A	21 212 DALYs	N/A	0.07
Ship emissions in Baltic Sea	Mwase et al. (2020) / PM	Sweden (2015) / 9.8 million	4 200 DALYs	43 DALY/10 ⁵	4.2
	Barregard et al. (2019) / PM _{2.5}	Sweden, Norway, Denmark, Finland, Germany, Poland, Estonia, Latvia, Lithuania, Russia (Baltic region) (2016) / N/A	17 987 DALYs	NA	0.08
Ship emission in Mediterranean coast	Viana et al. (2020) / PM _{2.5}	Eight European Mediterranean coastal cities (2007 to 2016)	432 deaths	66 YLL/10 ⁵	2.7
Electricity production	Zyśk et al. (2021) / PM _{2.5} , PM _{2.5-10} , SO ₂ , NO _x	Warsaw, PL (2018) / 1.77 million	PM10: 920 to 2590 YLL SO ₂ : 636 deaths NO _x : 1200 YLL	599 YLL/10 ⁵	0.30

(healthy) life year, or avoiding losing a (healthy) life year. The approach is used to combine human health and environmental damage in a unit that is easy to understand.

In the EU, one healthy life year (1 DALY) is commonly prized for 70,000 € (e.g., CE Delft, 2022, 2020). Schucht et al. (2021) estimated that air pollution damage, including greenhouse gases, range from 277 to 433 billion € in 2017 as the aggregated cost of industrial facilities as reported in E-PRTR. This included both human health and environmental damage. Road traffic related air pollution costs to human health (excluding environmental damage) in 432 European cities were over 166 billion € in 2018 (average 1,250 € per person per year) (CE Delft, 2020). The total health-related social costs of outdoor air pollution to human health (excluding environmental damage) due to domestic heating and cooking activities by households in the EU27+UK amounted to 29 billion € in 2018 (average 130 € per household per year) (CE Delft, 2022).

The monetary value of the NFM-industry air emissions at local scale would be 100.8 million € when excluding CO₂ and methane and environmental implication. This is more than 100 times lower than damage costs by traffic or domestic heating and cooking activities by households.

5. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The NFM-industry human health impact assessment was performed for aggregated NFM air emissions as reported in E-PRTR in 2019 and 2020. The assessment was performed at local scale by using the well-accepted BoD concept to quantify the health impact in terms of DALYs. The key values found in this study are summarized in Table 9. The health burden at local scale was estimated to be 1,440 DALYs (ca. 180 DALYs per 100,000 persons), which is low if compared to health impact caused by traffic, residential wood combustion, fossil fuels combustion in general, pig farming, and electricity production. External costs of human health burden were low as compared to emissions industry emissions in general, road traffic or domestic heating and cooking activities by households. Health impact evaluation shows that NFM-industry emissions impact is limited as compared to other sectors and the NFM-industry potential to improve the air quality is related to reduction of NO_x and PM emissions. Metal emissions associated with the activities of the NFM sector did not cause relevant health impact via direct air pollution exposure. Environmental impacts such as accumulation of metals to the environment, climate change potential, damage to structures and crops were not considered.

The study was performed by applying a precautionary approach without discounting or age-weighting on DALYs, cut-off concentration, or potential DALY double counting due to NO_x and PM health effects overlap. The evaluation's main drawback is the local scale impact assessment. A significant fraction of population exposure is not captured by the local exposure model because the ground level concentration was 25 µg/m³ at the model edges. Thus, an unknown fraction of health burden is not included in the assessment. The study can be strengthened by evaluating the large-scale NFM-facilities health impact at global scale and performing an aggregated analysis for small scale facilities, including the factories which may not need to report their emissions in E-PRTR. Linking the emissions with production data and data on economic output would enable cost-benefit assessment.

Despite the limitations of this study, the evaluation shows that the NFM-industry potential to reduce air pollution health effects is limited as compared to other key emission categories (sectors). It is recommended that a similar impact assessment is performed for the key emission categories as specified by EEA. Figure 6 for health burden would reveal the cause of air pollution impact on human health. An emission category specific health impact assessment would reveal cost-efficient mitigation methods to reduce the air pollution health burden. This would also help the general population to understand the causes for air pollution health impacts and to understand their responsibility for air quality as consumers. Assessment of health impacts and social benefits by emission category can be used to find mitigation methods having least impact on life quality, such as residential wood combustion in urban areas.

Currently EEA reports pollutant concentration maps, emissions by 'emission categories' and total health impacts as YLLs and premature deaths for PM_{2.5}, NO_x and O₃. The reporting can be extended to cover health impacts by emission categories as reported in E-PRTR and by "not-specified" category, which is the gap between the health impact attributable to the emissions reported under the E-PRTR and the health impact based on the concentration maps evaluated by field measurements and modellings (EEA, 2022d; EMEP/EEA,

2022). Such health impact assessment could be possibly automatized as well as the calculation of the total health burden for specific pollutants.

Table 9. Summary of the main findings.

Factor	NFM emissions	Reference value	Conclusion
NFM-sector annual reported emissions w/o CO ₂ and methane	0.545 Mt consisting of 89.5% CO, 6.8% NO _x , 2.1% SO _x , 1.1% NMVOC and 0.5% or other pollutants	EU-15 Member States 2020 emissions: NO _x 4.0 Mt, NMVOCs 4.6 Mt, SO _x 0.74 Mt, NH ₃ 2.6 Mt (EEA, 2022)	Major component for NFM industry emissions is CO when CO ₂ and methane are excluded. Emissions were low compared to main key emission categories.
Modelled average concentrations of NFM-sector emissions w/o CO ₂ and methane in 40 km by 40 km area	74.56 µg/m ³	CO concentration exceeded the EU AAQ standard of 10 µg/m ³ .	Ground level average concentrations were at the model edges <i>ca.</i> 25 µg/m ³ which shows population attributable exposure assessment was incomplete.
Average annual health burden in the model area (40 km by 40 km; 800 000 persons)	1,440 DALYs 180 DALYs per 10 ⁵ persons	4,097,900 YLL in EU-27 in 2019	Long transportation health impact was not assessed. Local impact covers 0.04% of EU-27 air pollution health burden.
Average risk level normalized as premature deaths	On average 0.12 premature deaths per factory/10 ⁵	1:100,000	Estimated for NFM-emissions exhausted from a single spot. NFM sector impact is low compared to other emission sectors. Acceptable impact per factory.
Monetary costs	108.8 million € w/o CO ₂ and methane and excluding environmental damage	Industry: 277 to 433 billion € (including greenhouse gases) Road traffic: 166 billion € Domestic heating and cooking activities by households: 29 billion €	Low monetary impact.

SUPPLEMENTARY MATERIAL

- Supplementary material 1: NFM-emissions, calculated concentrations, and calculation of DALYs
- Supplementary material 2: IMPACT simulation reports

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GLOSSARY

Term	Definition or meaning
Attributable burden	The disease burden attributed to a particular risk factor.
Baseline disease burden	Depends on the country or region, age classes, and gender. Disease burdens are reported by the Global Burden of Disease Collaborative Network (2020).
Disability duration	YLD consider the duration of the disease derived from e.g., health statistics, registries, and expert judgments.
Disability weights	Numerical representations of the severity of health loss associated with a health state. Derived from a worldwide, cross-cultural study to compare the relative severity of health problems, disability weights are numbers between (perfect health) to 1 (dead). The disability weights used for YLD are based on subjective measures, whereby the applied technique and the used panel (e.g. experts, patients or lay-people) have a strong influence on the obtained disability weights.
Disability-adjusted life year (DALY)	The sum of years lost due to premature death (YLLs) and years lived with disability (YLDs). DALYs are also defined as years of healthy life lost. The rationale and method of estimation are explained by WHO (2022).
Discount weight factors	DALYs can be counted in different metrics where 1) future health impacts are brought to present value assuming a constant discount rate of 3%; 2) health impacts in older and younger people are age-weighted and 3) the delay from current exposure to the manifestation of the associated disease, e.g. cancer (lag) is included in the discounting procedure. Age-weighting and time discounting are not anymore included in WHO DALY calculations (WHO, 2020).
Dispersion model	A dispersion model is a means of calculating air pollution concentrations using information about the pollutant emissions and the nature of the atmosphere. Dispersion model is used to assess how much an emission is likely to increase the ground level concentrations at distances from the source. Ground level concentrations are associated with population densities to calculate the population exposure fraction.
Emission-weighted average	A summary statistic representing the calculated properties of an aggregated NFM industry stack to give proportionally more weight to the values for stacks with higher emissions.
Exposure response function (ERF)	The relationship between the amount of exposure to a substance and the resulting changes in body function or health (response).
Global Burden of Disease (GBD)	In the 1990s, the World Health Organization (WHO), in co-operation with Harvard University and the World bank, developed a methodological concept to quantify the global burden of disease. The term burden of disease generally describes the total, cumulative consequences of a defined disease or a range of harmful diseases with respect to disabilities in a community. These consequences include health, social aspects, and costs to society. The gap between an ideal situation, where everyone lives free of disease and disability, and the cumulated current health status, is defined as the burden of disease; this was based to a large extent on statistical measurement of the DALY.
Ground level concentration	The concentration in air of a pollutant to which a human being is normally exposed. Ground level concentration is used to calculate population exposure without considering potential exposure reductions, e.g. by filtered ventilation air in indoor compartments.
Ideal health	Characterized by optimal levels of functioning or capacity in all the important domains of health, and freedom from any type of illness or disease. The “optimal” levels of functioning are defined as those levels above which further gains would not be regarded as improvements in health. States of exceptional functioning above these levels are thus considered to be talents or exceptional abilities, not higher states of health.

Key emission category	A key category is an emission source category that has a significant influence on an inventory. It may affect the absolute level of emissions, the trend in emissions or both. This report classifies categories jointly responsible for 80 % of the national total emissions of a given pollutant as key categories (EEA, 2022c).
PM _{2.5}	Mass per m ³ of particles passing through the inlet of size selective sampler with a transmission efficiency of 50% at an aerodynamic diameter of 2.5 µm.
PM _{2.5-10}	As above, with 10 µm and PM _{2.5} is subtracted. E-PRTR reports PM ₁₀ concentration which is here assumed to consist 50% of PM _{2.5} and 50% PM _{2.5-10} .
Population attributable fraction (PAF)	Proportional reduction in disease or injury that would occur if population exposure to a risk factor or group of risk factors were reduced to an alternative distribution.
Relative risk (RR)	Relative risk is a measure of the strength of an association. It is calculated as a ratio of the risk of occurrence of a disease or death among two population groups, such as those exposed to a risk factor and those not exposed.
Unit Risk (UR)	The upper-bound lifetime excess cancer risk estimated to result from continuous exposure to a toxic air contaminant at a concentration of 1 µg/m ³ in air. The interpretation of inhalation unit risk would be as follows: if unit risk = 2×10^{-6} per µg/m ³ , then two excess cancer cases are expected to develop per one million people if exposed daily for 70 years to one microgram of the toxic air contaminant per cubic meter of air.
Value of a life year (VOLY)	Based on people's willingness to pay for one additional (healthy) life year, or avoiding losing a (healthy) life year.
Years lived with disability (YLD)	Years of life lived with any short-term or long-term health loss.
Years of Life Lost (YLL)	Years of life lost due to premature mortality.

APPENDIX: DALY CALCULATIONS

PM_{2.5}, PM_{2.5-10}: NATURAL-CAUSE MORTALITY, COPD, IHD, RESPIRATORY DISEASES, ALRI (FOR PM_{2.5}), AND STROKE

The DALYs due to PM_{2.5} and PM_{2.5-10} were calculated according to Hänninen and Knol (2011):

$$RR^E = RR_u \frac{1}{E^t} \quad (1)$$

$$PAF = \frac{f \times (RR^E - 1)}{f \times (RR^E - 1) + 1} \quad (2)$$

$$DALY = PAF \times DALY_{baseline\ burden} \quad (3)$$

Where RR_u (-) is the relative risk per unit of exposure for natural-cause mortality, E^i ($\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$) is the exposure increment, E ($\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$) is the exposure level, f (-) is the fraction of the exposure population (here 1 as exposure is calculated as average concentrations), PAF (-) is the population attributable fraction, and $DALY_{baseline\ burden}$ is the baseline disease burden in DALYs for the specific health endpoint (Table 3). Relative risk for PM_{2.5} is assumed to follow the log-linear relationship which is applicable for PM_{2.5} concentrations below 35 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ (Pope et al., 2015).

For the natural cause-mortality a RR value of 1.08 (95% confidence interval (CI) 1.06-1.09) was used (Chen and Hoek, 2020). This is slightly higher than commonly applied value of 1.062 based on the recommendation of the World Health Organization (WHO) project “Health risks of air pollution in Europe—HRAPIE” (Héroux et al., 2015).

PM_{2.5}, PM_{2.5-10}: RADS, LRS FOR SCHOOL CHILDREN AND ADULTS

YLDs for morbidity outcomes were estimated with equations:

$$AI_k = E \times UR_k \times POP \quad (4)$$

$$DALY_k = AI_k \times DW_k \times D_k \quad (5)$$

Where k is disease, AI_k is the attributable incidence (number of new cases per year), E ($\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$) is the exposure level (PM_{2.5} or PM_{2.5-10}), UR_k ($1/\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$) is the unit risk, POP is the exposed population, DW_k is the disability weight, and D_k (years) is the duration of condition.

SO₂: LUNG CANCER

The DALYs due to SO₂ related lung cancers were calculated with equations 1, 2 and 3 where $DALY_{TBL}$ was 1665 per 10⁵ for all age groups and both sex in central Europe in 2019 (Table 3). The RR associated to 10 mg/m^3 change in SO₂ concentration was 1.01 (95% CI 0.94-1.08).

NO_x: NATURAL-CAUSE MORTALITY

The DALYs due to NO_x related natural mortality were calculated with equations 1 to 3 by using the HR value of 1.02 (95% CI 1.00-1.04) per 20 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ change in NO_x concentration. EEA assumes a cut-off value of 20 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ for NO₂ exposure meaning that exposures below the cut-off value are not calculated (EEA, 2017). Here

is assumed that the NO₂ baseline concentration level is above cut-off and additional exposure by stack emissions contribute to the natural-cause mortality.

CARBON MONOXIDE: ISCHEMIC HEART DISEASE

The change in ischemic heart disease due to chronic exposure to CO was calculated with equations 1,2 and 3 by where the RR associated to 1000 µg/m³ change in CO concentration was 1.01 (95% CI 0.94-1.08).

NICKEL: LUNG CANCER

The DALYs due to Ni related lung cancers were calculated with following equations:

$$AI = E \times UR \times POP \quad (6)$$

$$DALY_k = \frac{AI}{81.3} \times DALY_c / Death_c \quad (7)$$

Where E (µg/m³) is exposure to Ni, UR is a life time cancer risk of lung cancer per µg/m³ exposure, POP is the size of the study population and AI is the attributable incidence (number of new cases per year). The life time cancer risk of the population was divided with the average life span of 81.3 years to estimate new cases of cancers per year.

The DALY loss per lung cancer was estimated from the Global Burden of Disease 2019 Cancer Collaboration (2022). In 2019, tracheal, bronchus, and lung cancer (TBL) cancer were estimated to cause 45.9 million (95% uncertainty intervals (UI), 42.3-49.3 million) DALYs due to 2.26 million (95% UI, 2.07-2.45 million) incident TBL cases. Based on upper 95% UI and incident TBL cases, the mean *DALY_b* caused by a lung cancer is 21.8 (DALYs/cancer). The upper UI produces precautionary estimates for the cancer DALYs. The number of new cancer cases per year was converted to DALYs by multiplying the number of cases with the mean DALY loss of one lung cancer (21.8 DALYs per lung cancer death). For the UR a value of 2.4×10⁻⁴ cancers per µg/m³ exposure to Ni was used, based on the Bickel and Friedrich (2005).

COBALT: ADENOMA AND CARCINOMA

For adenoma, disability weights are not established. As a worst-case estimate, adenomas and carcinomas were treated similarly as lung cancer. The DALYs due to Co related adenomas and carcinomas were calculated with equations 6 and 7. For the UR a value of 0.003 cancers per µg/m³ exposure to Co was used, based on the Suh et al., (2016).

ANTIMONY: LUNG CANCER

The DALYs due to Sb related lung cancers were calculated with equations 6 and 7. For the UR a value of 1.2×10⁻⁷ cancers per µg/m³ exposure to Sb was used, based on the NRC (2000) where UR was assigned for the flame retardant mixture consists of about 66–75% decabromodiphenyl oxide and 25–33% antimony trioxide.

CHROMIUM AS CR(VI): LUNG CANCER

According to Krystek and Ritsema (2007), in industrial emission of a foundry up to 2% of the Cr was Cr(VI). Here it was assumed that 2% of Cr emissions contain Cr(VI) which DALYs due to Cr(VI) related lung cancers were calculated with equations 6 and 7. For the UR a value of 2.4×10⁻⁴ cancers per µg/m³ exposure to Cr(VI) was used, based on the Proctor et al., (2016).

CADMIUM: LUNG CANCER

The DALYs due to Cd related lung cancers were calculated with equations 6 and 7. For the UR a value of 0.003 cancers per $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ exposure to Cd was used, based on the Bickel and Friedrich (2005).

ARSENIC: LUNG CANCER

The DALYs due to As related adenomas and carcinomas were calculated with equations 6 and 7. For the UR a value of 1.5×10^{-4} cancers per $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ exposure to As was used, based on the (Erraguntla et al., 2012).

LEAD: A GENERIC APPROACH TO ESTIMATE MULTIPLE HEALTH ENDPOINTS

The most well-known health outcomes of Pb are neurological, renal, cardiovascular, hematological, immunological, reproductive, and developmental effects (ATSDR, 2020). Inorganic Pb compounds are classified as probably carcinogenic to humans (Group 2A). Exposure response functions for Pb exist for IQ loss, mild mental retardation, hypertensive diseases, increased blood pressure, IHD, cerebrovascular disease, and other cardiac diseases (Hänninen and Knol, 2011; Holnicki et al., 2017). However, here, the DALYs due to Pb related exposure was calculated by using a generic approach (Mainka and Fantke, 2022) to simplify the DALY calculations.

The generic approach is based on effect factors for Pb, EF_{Pb} (incidence risk/kg intake), which are derived from $ED50_{Pb}$ [kg/lifetime] as human lifetime dose for a population response of $\alpha_{\text{response}} = 50\%$, and combined with a generic severity factor of $SF = 11.5$ DALY/incidence for cancer effects and $SF = 2.7$ DALY/incidence for non-cancer effects (Huijbregts et al., 2005):

$$EF_{Pb} = \frac{\alpha_{\text{response}}}{ED50_{Pb}} \times SF \quad (8)$$

For cancer effects, $ED50_{Pb}$ correspond to human lifetime tumor dose, $TD50_{Pb}$, which is 20.4 kg/lifetime and for non-cancer effects $ED50_{Pb}$ is 0.058 kg/lifetime according to Mainka and Fantke (2022). The cancer effects for Pb are derived from rat oral exposure experiments and non-cancer effects from chronic human exposure via oral route as described by Mainka and Fantke (2022). The annual Pb intake, I_{Pb} ($\mu\text{g}/\text{year}$), is combined with cancer and non-cancer effects per exposure unit to obtain DALYs caused by Pb exposure $DALY_{Pb}$ (DALY/year):

$$DALY_{Pb} = I_{Pb} \times EF_{Pb}^{\text{cancer}} + EF_{Pb}^{\text{non-cancer}} \quad (9)$$

Intake was estimated from the relation between Pb air concentrations and blood Pb levels by using the approach by Bickel and Friedrich (2005) (see also Holnicki et al. 2017). Bickel and Friedrich (2005) estimated that $1.0 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ increase of Pb in the air leads to $50 \mu\text{g}/\text{L}$ increase in blood level Pb levels. If 60 kg adult contain 4.5 L blood, the effective intake excluding Pb accumulation to bones is $225 \mu\text{g}$ per $1.0 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ increase of Pb in the air. According to Eq. (9), this results to 4.6×10^{-6} DALY per $1.0 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ increase of Pb in the air, which was used as generic estimate of DALYs by Pb per exposed person.

BENZENE: LEUKEMIA

The DALYs due to C_6H_6 related leukemias were calculated with equations 6 and 7 where the UR is 6×10^{-6} cases of leukaemia per $1 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ in life time exposure. The life time cancer risk of the population was divided with the 81.3 years to estimate new cases of cancers per year by assuming the average life span of 81.3 years. The number of new cancer cases per year was converted to DALYs by assuming the same DALY loss as for lung cancer (21.8 DALYs per lung cancer death).

BENZO(A)PYRENE: LUNG CANCER

The DALYs due to BaP related lung cancers were calculated with equations 6 and 7. For the UR a value of 8.7×10^{-5} cancers per ng/m^3 exposure to BaP was used, based on the WHO (2000).

DIOXIN: TOTAL CANCER INCIDENCE

The DALYs due to dioxin related total cancer incidences were calculated with equations 6 and 7. UR was 0.001 cancers per $\text{pg}/\text{kg}/\text{d}$ for life time dioxin uptake based on the Hänninen and Knol (2011). The dioxin uptake to inhalation exposure was converted to concentration by using 60 kg body weight, 20 m^3 inhalation volume during 24-h exposure, and complete absorption of dioxin during inspiration and expiration (ECHA, 2012). This results to an inhalation unit risk of 0.003×10^{-6} cancers per $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ as a life time exposure to dioxin.

NAPHTHALENE: LUNG CANCER

The DALYs due to Naphthalene related lung cancers were calculated with equations 6 and 7. For the UR a value of 3.4×10^{-3} cancers per $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ exposure to Naphthalene was used, based on the (US-EPA, 2022).

POLYCHLORINATED BIPHENYLS (PCBS): LUNG CANCER

The DALYs due to PCBs related lung cancers were calculated with equations 6 and 7. For the UR a value of 0.1×10^{-3} cancers per $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ exposure to PCBs was used, based on the (US-EPA, 2022).

TETRACHLOROETHYLENE: LUNG CANCER

The DALYs due to Tetrachloroethylene related lung cancers were calculated with equations 6 and 7. For the UR a value of 2.6×10^{-7} cancers per $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ exposure to Tetrachloroethylene was used, based on the (US-EPA, 2022).

TRICHLOROETHYLENE (TRI): LUNG CANCER

The DALYs due to TRI related lung cancers were calculated with equations 6 and 7. For the UR a value of 4.1×10^{-6} cancers per $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ exposure to TRI was used, based on the (US-EPA, 2022).

DICHLOROMETHANE: HEPATIC, RESPIRATORY CANCER

The DALYs due to dichloromethane related lung cancers were calculated with equations 6 and 7. For the UR a value of 1×10^{-8} cancers per $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ exposure to dichloromethane was used, based on the US EPA (2011).

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